

In vivo evaluation of a newly designed biodegradable magnesium alloy bone implant

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Abstract:

Objectives : a patent Mg-6 wt% Zn-0.3 wt% Ca alloy with adequate strength and controllable degradation rate was developed as potential candidate for orthopedic implantation. In vivo osseous regeneration capability of the implant via follow up bone density radiography was evaluated and the effect of its degradation on blood biochemistry was assessed periodically

Methods: A total eight cylindrical rods with 15 ± 0.4 mm length and 4 ± 0.2 mm diameter were machined from as-cast Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca alloy and implanted surgically in the femur bone in the mongrel dogs after being anesthetized. Analysis of blood biochemistry and radiographic examination for bone densitometric analysis around the Mg implants were followed up post-operative immediately till the end of the study period (3 months).

Results: Biochemical blood analysis for implanted Mg-alloy revealed overall stabilization in electrolytes (Mg, Zn and Ca). Adding to that, kidney and liver function parameters were fallen within the normal range. On the other hand, densitometrical measurements of the newly formed bone around Mg implants revealed that the highest significant bone density was recorded at first and second time intervals (2 & 4 weeks) after implantation when compared with the normal bone. The X-ray image at the second, third, and fourth time intervals showed circumferential periosteal reaction around the Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca alloy rods indicating the formation of new bone.

Conclusions: An innovative Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca alloy is suitable for biomedical orthopedic applications because of its controlled biodegradability and adequate strength. It was proven that the investigated Mg- based alloy promotes newly bone formation that had neither adverse effect on blood biochemistry nor kidney and liver functions.

Key words: Magnesium alloy, biodegradable, blood analysis, peri-implant bone response.

Introduction

Innovative degradable biomaterials are currently one of the most interesting research topics. The paradigm that based on using only corrosion resistant metallic implants has been broken by the advent of this new class of biomaterials [1]. They have been considered a new class of bioactive materials which are expected to support the healing process of a diseased tissue or organ and in sequence gradually degrade [2,3].

Magnesium alloys are attractive candidates as biodegradable orthopedic implants in load bearing clinical applications due to their excellent mechanical properties, inherent biocompatibility as well as stimulation of bone formation [4, 5]. Elastic modulus of magnesium alloys are about 40–45 GPa, close to that of human bone (10–20 GPa), which can reduce stress shielding effect, thus, preventing bone resorption [6, 7]. However, rapid degradation rate of Mg- alloy represents an obstacle. They tend to corrode too quickly in the physiological environment ($\text{pH} = 7.4\text{--}7.6$), thereby fast degradation induces early loss of mechanical integrity before hard tissue repair occurs which typically requires for a minimum of 12 weeks [8,9].

Magnesium alloys with controlled corrosion rate are targeted as implant material in weight bearing bones [11]. One of the most successful methods to control corrosion rate is to alloy the material with different elements. The elements as aluminum (Al) and/or rare earth (RE) such as Pr, Ce, Y, etc. are commonly used [12]. In general, these elements improve the mechanical and physical properties of magnesium alloys [13] but (Al) has a destructive effect on neurons and associated with Alzheimer's

disease [14] and (RE) is closely associated with liver, lung, breast and nasopharyngeal cancers [15, 16]. Therefore, another new magnesium alloy system containing nontoxic or low toxic element have been developed. Alloying Mg with Ag, In, Si, Sn, Zn, and Ca, could diminish the neurotoxic effect and improve both the strength and corrosion rate of magnesium alloys [17, 18].

Previous studies have been demonstrated that properties and biocompatibility of Mg–Ca binary alloy can be modified by controlling the Ca content [5, 6,17]. However, insufficient mechanical properties as well as inferior corrosion resistance are the two major drawbacks. Later, Mg–Zn system has been paid more attention because Zinc is one of abundant nutritional elements in human bodies [19]. Moreover, it is believed that Zinc as an alloying ingredient contributes to strength due to solid solution strengthening mechanism [2].

Mg-Zn-Ca ternary alloys seem promising because of the biological metabolism and excretion of the alloying elements [21, 22]. Thus, in this study, a patent Mg- based ternary alloy composed of essential elements in human body; Mg-Zn-Ca, with adequate mechanical properties and slow degradation rate was developed as potential candidate for orthopedic implantation. In vivo osseous regeneration capability of this biodegradable magnesium implant via follow up bone density radiography was evaluated and the effect of its degradation on blood biochemistry was assessed periodically.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

A recent Mg-alloy with a nominal composition of Mg-6 wt.% Zn-0.3 wt.% Ca was prepared using pure magnesium (99.8%), high purity zinc (99.97%), and high purity calcium (99.99%) metals (Central Metallurgical Research and Development Institute (CMRDI), Helwan, Egypt). The chemical composition of the alloy as determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analyzer (Rigaku, Portrix, Japan), are given in Table 1. A total of eight cylindrical rods with 15 ± 0.4 mm length and 4 ± 0.2 mm diameters were machined from the as-cast alloy for animal implantation. All samples were polished with SiC paper up to #1200 grit and were washed with 70 vol% ethanol at room temperature, cleaned ultrasonically (JULBO, LABORTEVHNIK GMBH, Germany) in distilled water for 5 minutes and then, dried by air drier (BRAUN, Germany). Prior to surgical procedure, it was mandatory to sterilize the cylindrical rod samples. The implants were exposed to the specific γ -radiation sterilization dose of 2.5 mega rad in the range of 1.0023 KGY/hr (60 Co, Baha, Baha Indian Cobalt-60-4000A, National Center for Radiation Research and Technology NCRRT, Cairo, Egypt) [23]. Then, these implants were kept in sterile packages till usage.

2.2. Animal study

The in vivo experiments were performed in a veterinary theatre at the Department of Surgery, Anesthesiology and Radiology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Cairo University, Egypt in accordance to, and approved by the "Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC)" of faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Cairo University.

2.2.1. Surgical procedure

A total of four skeletally mature mongrel male dogs with an average age 20 ± 2 months old and weighing 15-18 kg were used in this study. The dogs were fasted for 12 hours and premedicated with intramuscular injection (I.M.) of chlorpromazine hydrochloride in a dose of 1 mg/kg, 15 min prior to the induction of general anesthesia. The hair coat was clipped and shaved, washed with water and soap then painted with 10% Povidone-Iodine (Betadine®, Nile pharm, Egypt.). Finally, general anesthesia was conducted by intravenous injection of thiopental sodium 2.5%, 500mg (Egyptian INT. pharmaceutical industries Co., E.I.P.I.C.O.).

The right femur was completely exposed by a lateral skin incision and blunt dissection of the muscles. After complete exposure of the femur, two holes were drilled in the lower extremity of the femur to receive two Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca alloy rods. A size 4 rose round head bur was used to locate and initially perforate the implant site with low speed and saline coolant. The hole was extended through the cortex into cancellous bone. Two adjacent implant holes with appropriate distance among them were prepared using a progressive sequence of spiral drills (Superline, Implantium Company, UK). The drilling procedures were performed at speeds less than 1500 rpm under copious irrigation of sterile saline to reduce the risk of thermal bone damage due to overheating. The initial drilling was performed by 2 mm diameter pilot drill at 1200 rpm; then, slower speed of 800 rpm for sequential drilling with burs of 2.5, 3.0, 3.5 mm. The implant sites were prepared to a depth of 11 mm such that they were parallel to each other to individually facilitate sectioning of each implant later. At the end, the implants were carefully handled to avoid contact contamination. They were press fit into the osteotomy sites by manual light pressure and with a regular up-and-down motion in order to maximize access of the saline to the full depths of the implant hole to wash bone debris. A balanced electrolyte solution (0.9% sodium chloride; I.V. infusion B.P.2000, ElNasr pharmaceutical chemicals co. Adwia, Egypt) was administered in amount of 10 ml/kg/hr throughout surgical procedures. Finally, the surgical site was irrigated with saline

mixed with gentamycin (Gentamycin®, Amoun, Egypt). The wound layers were repositioned and sutured using absorbable suture material Vicryl (0) (Vicryl®: Polyglactin, Ethicon Ltd., U.K.).

Each experimental animal was injected postoperatively with 1g of amoxicillin (I.M.) (E.Mox: Egyptian International Pharm. Industries Company, Egypt) and dipyron in a dose of 10 mg/kg I.M. for 5 days (Analgin 50%: El-Nasr pharmaceutical Chemicals Co., Egypt.). Every dog was set aside in separate cage and allowed for water free choice till gradually returned to full feed over the next 48 hours. All dogs were subjected to daily clinical examination, including evidence of infection, local reaction and regional lymph node enlargement. The surgical stitches were removed after 10 days. The experimental animals were euthanized at two, four, eight and twelve weeks after rods implantation surgery by an overdose of thiopental.

2.4.2. Blood biochemical analysis

A 5 mL blood sample was taken from each experimental animal before implantation and bi-weekly throughout the study. The blood samples were centrifuged and the serum was analyzed to measure the change of serum magnesium, zinc and calcium level after the operation. The kidney functions were monitored by checking urea and creatinine levels in the serum, whereas liver functions were monitored by checking serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), and serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT) levels in the serum.

2.4.3. Radiographic examination

Radiographs were made immediately, post-operatively and at 2 weeks interval till the end of the experiment at 12 weeks to observe the in vivo degradation process during the experiments. For determination of the bone density, densitometric Digora software (Orion Corp. Sordex medical system, Finland) was used to measure the mean density value along a line or an area of controlled dimensions. The term density refers to the degree of blackness of the image or part of it. Bone density along three lines around each implant was recorded individually and then the mean of the readings was calculated for further bone quality evaluation [24].

2.5. Statistical Analysis

The collected data of bone density were statistically analyzed by using SPSS version 16, statistical package for social science. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to compare among various investigated groups intervals, followed by the least significant difference (LSD) test at 95% level of confidence (P-value is < 0.05).

3. Results

3.1. Blood biochemistry

The variations in serum Mg, Ca, Zn, urea, creatinine, glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), and glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT) of the dogs after different implantation durations are shown in figure 1. The data indicated an overall stabilization of the level of Mg during the three months period of implantation as the value obtained in last week (the 12th week) was 2.4 mg/dl taking in consideration that the reference range is 1.6-2.4 mg/dl. Meanwhile the same profile was obtained in Ca as the last reading (the 12th week) was 9.25 mg/dl and the reference range is 8.9-11.4 mg/dl. For Zn, the highest value 194 μ g/dl was obtained in the 10th week and the reference range is 70-200 μ g/dl. For kidney-related parameters (creatinine and urea) and liver function parameters (SGOT and SGPT) were fallen within the normal range.

3.2. Radiographic evaluation

Means, standard deviations and results of LSD test of the densitometrical measurements of the newly formed bone around the magnesium alloys implanted in the experimental animals are presented in Table 2. The data revealed that; the highest bone density was recorded after two weeks (first time interval) from

implantation; 12.10 ± 0.13 . This record was decreased after one month from implantation (second time interval) and two months (third time interval) to be insignificant with immediately bone after implantation; 11.68 ± 0.23 , 11.63 ± 0.23 and 11.55 ± 0.20 respectively. The decrease in density was continued, as a significant decrease was recorded after three months (fourth time interval); 10.51 ± 0.35 . A diffuse gas shadow (arrow in Figure. 2b) was observed in soft tissues around the magnesium alloy rods at two weeks. One month post-implantation, the gas shadow spontaneously disappeared (Figure. 2c). The X-ray image at the second, third, and fourth time intervals showed circumferential periosteal reaction around the Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca alloy rods indicating the formation of new bone "osteogenesis" (yellow triangle in Figure. 2c, d, and e).

4. Discussion

Magnesium alloys have attracted great attention as an orthopedic biodegradable implant material because of their perfect biocompatibility and close mechanical properties to those of natural bone. From the biocompatibility standpoint, in-vivo degradation of an implanted alloy denotes its liability to release some elements that would trigger the biological response of the surrounding tissues i.e. implant/ tissue reaction at the interface[25]. In the present study, biochemical blood analysis for the implanted Mg6Zn0.3Ca alloys revealed overall stabilization of the level of the measured electrolytes (Mg, Zn and Ca). Adding to that, kidney and liver function parameters were fallen within normal range. The regulation of electrolytes (Mg, Zn and Ca) occurs in the kidneys where the electrolytes present in the plasma are filtered in the glomerulus with just over 95% being reabsorbed. The reabsorbed amount is controlled mainly by its concentration in plasma. Excess electrolytes (Mg, Zn and Ca) in serum are excreted through the kidneys [26, 27]. It is reasonably concluded that the released elements due to biodegradation of the implanted Mg-alloys had no adverse effect on blood biochemistry, liver and kidney functions of the experimental animals.

One of the valuable methods for bone assessment is the radiographic densitometry. Minerals content of bone are heavy elements rendering the bone radiopaque. Depending on the amount of minerals, the radio-opacity will differ and could be monitored by x-ray. Densitometric measurements of the newly

formed bone around Mg alloy rods revealed that the highest significant bone density was recorded at the first and the second time intervals after implantation. The bone density was also significantly higher than normal bone; in these intervals periods (2wks and 4wks; respectively); (Table. 2). At the end of the study, there was a significant decrease of bone density around the implant less than the normal bone. These finding can be explained as follow: when the magnesium implant was inserted into bone, the implant was surrounded immediately by a large amount of blood. A blood clot formed and hematoma was stabilized and organized around the implant. Blood is a Ca²⁺, PO₄⁻, and Cl⁻-containing solution. A reaction between magnesium alloys and blood occurred on the surface of the magnesium implant. As a result, a calcium magnesium phosphate layer was formed around magnesium implant [28]. The formation of this layer would protect magnesium implant from fast corrosion or degradation, and might improve its surface osteoconductivity. Then, osteoblast cells attached and adhered to the phosphate surface, proliferated, differentiated, and calcified. As well, magnesium ions enhance the cell attachment and proliferation. Finally, the new bone is formed on the surface of the magnesium implant. The obtained results were in concordance with Witte et al.[29] and Höh et al.[30]. It should be pointed out that hydrogen gas detected in the radiographic film at the first interval is self-absorbed because the gas shadows were not observed at the second time interval; (Figure. 2c). These results were consistent with the in vivo investigations of other magnesium alloys studied by Li et al.[5]; Zhang et al.[30]; Ikee et al.[31] where the hydrogen gas bubbles appeared at one week post-operative and disappeared later.

5. Conclusion

Under the circumstances of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Fabrication of Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca alloy is considered an innovative approach for biodegradable platforms in biomedical orthopedic application.
- On top of the stimulated newly formed bone, the controlled biodegradation of the investigated Mg – based alloy needs no second operation for implants' removal.
- It was proven that the investigated Mg- based alloys have neither adverse effect on blood biochemistry nor kidney and liver functions

Table 1: Chemical composition of the Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca alloy

Material	Chemical composition (wt. %)				
	Zn	Ca	Fe	Cu	Mg
Mg-6Zn-0.3Ca	6.63	0.282	0.031	0.042	balance

Table 2: Means, standard deviations and results of LSD test for the densitometric measurements of the newly formed bone around the magnesium alloy implants surfaces in the experimental animals

Time interval	Mean ± SD	P-value
Intact bone	11.55±0.19 ^b	<0.0001
1 st time interval	12.10±0.13 ^a	
2 nd time interval	11.68±0.23 ^b	
3 rd time interval	11.63±0.23 ^b	
4 th time interval	10.51±0.35 ^c	

Means with the same superscript letters are not significantly different

Figure 1: Serum biochemical values of (a) Magnesium; (b) Calcium; (c) Zinc; (d) Creatinine; (e) Urea; (f) SGPT; and (g) SGOT. The dashed lines in (a-g) represent the reference range for serum biochemical levels in dogs.

- **Figure 2:** Femora radiographs representing a case through the study period; immediately after surgery till the end of 12th week. The yellow triangle marks the periosteal reaction around the implantation site while the arrow marks the gas shadows.

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